

Machine Learning the Steam Video Game Database

Subash Pandey

Department of Computer Science

University of Exeter

Exeter, UK

sp915@exeter.ac.uk

Abstract—With a wide variety of game genres available to suit different player interests, the video game business has experienced exponential expansion in recent years. In order to investigate the connections between game genres in the Steam Video Game Database, this research explores the nexus of network science and machine learning. This study attempts to reveal hidden patterns, relationships, and insights inside the database by building a bipartite genre based network. Data gathering and pre-processing for the project begin with the extraction of game details from the Steam Database, such as game titles, genres, and user reviews. The game entries are arranged into a bipartite network, with nodes denoting genres and edges denoting genre co-occurrences. To identify the most significant genres and genre clusters, network analysis approaches including centrality measures and community detection are used. The data is then used to predict user ratings using machine learning. Numerous regression models are applied and tested, revealing the factors that have the greatest influence on user ratings. This study expands our understanding of how game genres relate to player preferences. Network analysis sheds light on genre interactions and their impact on game popularity. Machine learning methods provide a quantitative technique to predicting user ratings, highlighting the genres that have the most impact on interaction. Finally, this interdisciplinary approach gives a thorough framework for comprehending the complex terrain of game genres and their importance in player engagement. These insights, which are useful to developers, marketers, and researchers, can help them make judgements about genre trends, game design, and user interaction techniques in the ever-changing video game business.

Index Terms—Steam, video games, Network analysis, Genre evolution, Community detection, Popularity prediction

I. INTRODUCTION

The landscape of the video game industry has changed quickly in recent years, offering a wide variety of game genres to suit the various interests of gamers throughout the world. The variety and complexity of video game genres have expanded at an unprecedented pace as a result of the convergence of quickly developing technology, intelligent game design, and extensive player communities [1], [2]. Game developers, researchers, and other industry stakeholders must now prioritise understanding the connections between different genres and how they affect player involvement in this dynamic context [3]. Through the use of network science and machine learning tools, this project seeks to explore the complex web of video game genres and their connections. The Steam Video Game Database, a comprehensive and detailed collection of game titles, genres, and game properties, serves as the project's focal point. The fundamental question driving this research

is: How can we harness the power of network analysis and machine learning to analyse genre evolution and uncover the underlying patterns and trends in the relationships between video game genres and user engagement?

The creation of a genre-based network, which not simply maps the co-occurrence of genres but also depicts their temporal growth, is a key technical aspect of this research. This study explains the dynamic nature of player preferences and the growth of genres over time by examining the changes in genre relationships over time. This offers a priceless viewpoint on how genres adapt and flourish within the always changing context of the video game business. This project enhances our understanding of how game properties affect player engagement by utilising machine learning approaches. It evaluates the effect of game properties on player acceptance by using prediction models to anticipate user evaluations based on game properties and values. This research has ramifications beyond gaming as it clarifies the variables influencing player happiness and game popularity and provides information on how different player demographics respond to different games.

The conclusions drawn from this study go beyond gaming to encompass broader sociological, cultural, and economic spheres. The genre-based network analysis examines how gaming genres interact with cultural trends, social dynamics, and economic environments [4], [5]. Understanding which genres are successful and how they interact can provide insights into society dynamics and cultural preferences, influencing the direction of game development in the future and market strategies. Game designers, marketers, and industry decision-makers now have access to a toolkit thanks to the culmination of network science and machine learning insights. This project provides stakeholders with a thorough grasp of genre evolution, player involvement, and societal relevance so they can make wise decisions. These findings contain the potential to guide business choices that resonate with players and support the expansion of the industry, from designing games that correspond with emerging genre patterns to defining marketing strategies.

Finally, this project makes technical advances that go beyond those related to gaming and user interaction. The integration of network science and machine learning methods reveals the dynamics of genres in the world of video games and also provides insights into genre evolution, the manner in which genres affect player preferences, social and cultural trends, and economic ramifications. The conclusions have an impact

on game development, marketing, and player engagement initiatives by giving the industry a basis for making evidence-based decisions.

II. BACKGROUND

The video game industry has undergone significant shifts through the decades, experiencing immense growth, technological innovation, and increased competition. What was once niche, appealing mainly to young tech enthusiasts, has transformed into mainstream entertainment spanning all demographics [6]. As gaming evolved, the market shifted from traditional PC games to social, casual genres, fostering exponential growth [7]. Categorizing games based on shared attributes rather than visuals recognizes their contemporary media role, intertwined with cultural practices and societal importance [8]. Understanding consumer demographics, social rituals, and ideological development becomes vital due to genres' cultural and social impacts. Sifa in this study [9] indicates no minimal correlation between game reviews and play time or consumer engagement. Faisal in this study [10] says psychometric analysis helps track player behavior shifts, revealing social consequences. Zammito's work [11] connects gaming preferences with personality traits and user clusters. Heintz [12] says analyzing genre networks compares effectiveness and identifies evolutionary links.

Network Science sits at the core of this research as it forms the basis for Genre-Network Creation and analysis. Network science is an emerging, extremely multifaceted field of study with the goal of creating theoretical and practical methods and strategies to improve our comprehension of both natural and artificial networks [13]. The essence of Network Science is its implementation of graphs and sub-graphs that have a certain structure/topology and carry additional information such as types, weights and node attributes [14]. In our research, the network is a weighted graph commonly known as a bipartite network. A bipartite graph is one in which the vertex set may be divided into two disjoint subgroups and the two end points of each edge are drawn from distinct vertex sets. A bipartite network may simply model two distinct collections of components and their relationships [15]. Bipartite networks can be seen all around us like customer-product relationship, research affiliation, disease-gene networks and others [16]. Further to segregate the two subsets of nodes, the two-mode network between the different nodes is to be collapsed into an unipartite network to focus on implications of singular set of node on another node set. In one-mode projection, the connection between the vertices on one side of a bipartite graph is used to project the vertices on the other side of the network. The lost side of the bipartite graph is then assigned as edge weights in the new unipartite network [17]. The use of one-mode projection in a bipartite network of miRNA-Disease to generate the bias rating from illness to miRNA and the bias rating from miRNA to disease based on integrated miRNA similarity and integrated disease similarity is demonstrated in this study [18]. Similarly paper [19] showcases use of a weighted bipartite graph's one mode projection for item rec-

ommendation, which offers greater recommendation accuracy than certain other similarity-based approaches. This paper [20] uses Network science to view the evolution of collaboration patterns in music genres.

Communities, also known as clusters, are often groups of vertices that are more likely to be connected with one another than to vertices of other groups, though different patterns are possible [21]. Clustering was used in this study [22] on a two-mode network of artists and respondents to discover groups of persons who have comparable relationships to the same sets of artists. They were able to identify music liking trends and social distinctions in these response clusters in this manner. Ardanuy in this study [23] performs clustering on a vector of network about novel genre and authorship to identify the relationship between these attributes of a novel. Xiaozhou in this paper [24] implements network analysis on steam game tags to gain a better understanding of Game genres and also implements centrality measures and community detection.

This paper [25] mentions use of Weighted Kernel Logistic Regression for classification of video genre, and is able to predict genre with significant accuracy. The researchers use the steam platform data to predict the popularity of games, and further implement Bayesian approach to understand the influence of a game's price, size, supported languages, release date, and genres on its player count [26]. Teja [27] in this research uses Linear Regression, Random Forest Regression and Decision Tree Regression to predict game ratings based on steam data, attaining a model with R-squared score greater than 0.9. Zhang [28] in this paper uses multiple linear regression to predict game sales, and finds average discount variable to be an important factor in increasing sales of a video game.

III. AIMS & OBJECTIVES

The project's main goal is to analyse the Steam Video Game Database in-depth in order to draw important conclusions that shed light on the dynamic evolution of video game genres. The project's goal in conducting this investigation is to identify developing factors that are reshaping the gaming industry's landscape as well as past trends. The project's overarching goal is to use data science approaches to significantly contribute to the expansion and advancement of the video game industry. The initiative aims to offer a distinctive viewpoint for cultural research and computational social science inside the gaming industry by utilising data-driven insights. To address these objectives, a series of pertinent research questions are posed:

- a How has the intricate tapestry of video game genres and sub-genres evolved over time, and what factors have been instrumental in shaping this evolution?
- b By delving into the ratings, popularity metrics, and player demographics, the project aims to discern the most popular video game genres and sub-genres. This analysis seeks to unravel the comparative success factors across these categories.
- c Exploring the interrelationships among various genres and sub-genres is a core inquiry. This will illuminate

the intricate web of connections that exist, potentially revealing unexpected correlations.

- d A noteworthy endeavor involves the development of predictive models that estimate the playtime of diverse video games as they unfold over time. The project also endeavors to identify pivotal elements that exert influence on a game’s playtime and overall popularity.
- e Beyond the immediate gaming sphere, the project aims to unravel the profound impact of genres and sub-genres on broader cultural, social, and technological trends. This exploration will provide context to the gaming industry’s role in shaping the world at large.

In line with these research questions, the project’s objectives crystallize:

- a A comprehensive investigation into the Steam Video Game Database will be undertaken, aimed at deciphering the most favored game genres and their sub-genres within the platform. This analysis will further encompass the tracking of their evolutionary trajectories.
- b Through meticulous scrutiny, the project will illuminate the intricate relationship between ratings, player demographics, and the triumph or decline of various video game genres and sub-genres.
- c Employing advanced machine learning algorithms, the project will endeavor to develop models capable of prognosticating game playtime, grounded in the inherent properties of each game.
- d The project’s scope extends to the realm of societal and technological forces. It aims to shed light on the role of these influences in the emergence and evolution of video game genres and sub-genres, ultimately identifying the driving catalysts behind industry transformation.

IV. EXPERIMENT DESIGN & METHODS

The experiment design follows a pipeline of data pre-processing, Exploratory Data Analysis, Bipartite Network creation and projection, Network Analysis and finally Regression.

A. Data Pre-processing & Exploratory Data Analysis

The dataset chosen for this research is the Steam Store Games¹ data, made available by "Nik Davis"² on Kaggle. The data has a temporal coverage date till 05/02/2019. The data is licensed under Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)³ which allows me to share and adapt the data for any work I want to build on top of it. The data holds 27075 unique values and 18 columns. The data contains information on different games available in the Steam platform and provides information on their ID, name, release date, availability of the game in English language, the developers and publishers of the game, platforms the game is available in, the required age to play the game, the categories, genres and tags the game is associated with. Followed by these attributes are

quantitative attributes such as number of achievements in the game, positive or negative ratings the game has received, median and average playtime for the game, range of owners that own the game and finally the price of the game.

The data required minimal pre-processing as it had no duplicate or null values to start with. The different genres a game is related to was provided as values separated by ‘;’. These values were split and exploded into separate rows to relate each row of game to a unique genre. This helped prepare the data for Network Creation. For the Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA), the correlation between different variables was viewed to identify highly-correlated variables in the data. Unique values in attributes such as release year, platforms, availability of English language were visualized to get a grasp of data being dealt with. Finishing up with the data processing and EDA, the data was readied for network creation and projection.

B. Bipartite Network and Multi-mode Projection

A Bipartite Network $G = (\nu_1, \nu_2, \epsilon)$ can be defined as a network having two different type of nodes: $\nu_1 = \{v_{1_1}, v_{1_2}, ..v_{1_U}\}$ and $\nu_2 = \{v_{2_1}, v_{2_2}, ..v_{2_M}\}$. These nodes are of sizes U and M respectively and are referred as partite sets. The edges in the network only lie between nodes of different type [29]. Likewise the Steam Video Games Dataset can be described as a bipartite network with genres and games as distinct node types, and edges to represent connection between a game and a genre. If the set of X games is $\chi = \{\chi_1, \chi_2, \dots, \chi_X\}$, the set of Y genres is $\Upsilon = \{\Upsilon_1, \Upsilon_2, \dots, \Upsilon_Y\}$ and the set of connections $\epsilon = \{e_{(1,1)}, e_{(1,2)}, \dots, e_{(X,Y)}\}$, then the dataset can be represented as network $N = (\chi, \Upsilon, \epsilon)$. The adjacency matrix of the network is $G \in \mathbb{R}^{X \times Y}$, where $G(i, j)$ is the connection of game i to genre j and zero if such connection does not exist. The bipartite network is created using NetworkX. The bipartite network N can be showcased as in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: Illustration of Bipartite Graph of Genre and Games

Following the creation of bipartite graphs for Genre and Game nodes, Multi-mode projection will be implemented to project the two nodes separately. Our research’s primary focus is on evolution and impact of genres, thus the Υ – projection of the bipartite graph N will be focused with weights of this uni-partite graph being the common neighbors in χ and Υ . The

¹<https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/nikdavis/steam-store-games>

²<https://www.kaggle.com/nikdavis>

³<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Multimode Projection in this research is performed on Gephi using the Multimode network plugin. The projection is based on the matrix multiplication approach where the matrices are Genre to Games on the left matrix and Games to Genre on the right matrix, followed by removal of nodes and edges of collapsed network. The projection performed to gain the weighted uni-partite Genre network is shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2: Illustration of a bipartite network (a), with its X-projection (b) and Y-projection (c) [15]. Image reproduced with permission of the rights holder, American Physical Society.

C. Network Analysis

1) *Centrality Measures and Network Visualization:* Following the creation of one-mode genre network, the topological attributes of the new graph is analysed. Attributes like number of nodes and edges in the projected network, average number of neighbors for each genre node, density of the projected graph, and number of connected components is viewed. Then, centrality measures are implemented on the network to identify the most important genres based on influence, connectivity and information flow [30]. The network after being projected is exported as graph file to Jupyter notebook, where NetworkX is used to implement the various centrality measures on the data. I implement Degree Centrality, Closeness Centrality, Betweenness Centrality and Eigenvector centrality which results in a list of genre having high scores in these measures. The number of neighbors for each genre with high centrality measure is also viewed. For the visualization of different centrality measures and the overall network, the projected graph is imported into a new workspace on Gephi, where the the graph is laid out using 'Fruchterman-Reingold' layout; a force-directed layout that positions the genre nodes in a way to minimize edge crossings and to maximize the aesthetic of the topology. The 'Average Weighted Degree' statistic is run for the network to get the degree distribution report and to be able to color the nodes based on their ranking for different centrality measures. For each centrality measure, the graph is colored based on the ranking of genre nodes. The 'label adjust' layout is ran finally to make the labels not collapse on each other and are exported in a way to showcase the nodes, edges and labels clearly.

2) *Genre Evolution:* The essence of this research is to capture the changes and dynamics of different genres through different time periods and how they interact with one another [31]. In our research, the total temporal coverage is split into 5-year periods to gain insight on genre dynamics and connections covering this time spans from start to finish of temporal coverage of the data. A total of 5 different graph files were produced for 5 different time spans using NetworkX and the projected network, which were imported into Gephi to analyse temporal changes. These separate graphs were analysed separately based on their structure, properties and weights carried by the genre nodes connecting one another. For each graph file, the graphs are imported into Gephi, then the graphs are laid out on 'Fruchterman-Reingold' layout. Further the node sizes of different genres were mandated based on the degree centrality of each genre node i.e., higher degree centrality meaning a bigger node size and vice-versa. This was performed to highlight the important nodes based on centrality measure. Further, the different networks were clustered using Louvain Algorithm which iterates through the nodes and changes their community based on change in modularity [32]. After that the algorithm agglomerates different communities into one node and finally are partitioned as different communities in the network. The first three graphs ranging from 1995 to 2010 were clustered using resolution of 1.0 as the graph was sparse and existence of many communities was not expected. But for the last two graphs ranging from 2010 to 2020 were clustered using resolution of 0.5 as the genres were abundant and existence of many communities was expected. Genres with frequent interaction are also highlighted with this approach providing us valuable information on related genres, or genres that experience similar trends. A genre hierarchy is also created to display the emergence of sub-genres from an existing genre. The hierarchy or the assignment of a child-genre is based on two conditions which analyses the relationship between any two genres. The conditions are:

- 1) If the child genre and the parent genre share the same community in the era of emergence of child genre.
- 2) If the child genre has the highest weight or number of connections from the parent-genre.

If these two conditions are met for any two genres, a connection is drawn from the older genre to the younger genre, as it highlights the emergence of a new sub-genre, and also indicates the genre that firstly incorporated emerging genres. This provides us valuable information on emergence or incorporation of genres through different time periods and also helps track popularity of a certain genre. It also helps us identify any trends that were existent in a certain time period that pushed the developer to incorporate certain properties of an emerging genre in their games to push consumer engagement. It also adds to the analysis of social and cultural impact of games in different time periods.

3) *Community Detection:* Community Detection or Clustering is performed by loading the GraphML data onto Gephi which consists of the projected network. Firstly, the node

sizes are set based on the weighted degree of each genre, with a higher degree meaning a larger node size to highlight the more important nodes. Then the 'Fructerman-Reingold' layout is used on the network to make the graph more visually appealing. The community detection plugin is installed from the tools menu, which come under the statistics bar. Since, the community detection is to be performed on the complete dataset i.e., all genre, all genres are selected to be clustered. Further, Modularity clustering is performed with a resolution of 0.5 to capture the different communities in the genre network. Performing the modularity clustering generate partitions for different communities which are then applied to the genre nodes as nodes color to display different communities as different partitions [33]. Following the partition, adjustments like node label size, edge thickness are implemented to the visualization. Finally, the visualization is exported for further analysis and presentation.

4) *Node attributes*: Node attributes in a network help provide additional context and details for each node [34]. In our context, two genre attributes are added to the genre network to help represent the Median Play time and Net Ratings received by each genre. These attributes help enrich the understanding of nodes and their relationship within the network. Firstly the variable "Net ratings" is computed by subtracting the positive ratings by negative ratings received by each genre in the original dataset. Then two different dataframes are constructed to group the genres and sum up the net ratings and median play time value for each genre. These two dataframes are converted into dictionaries with genre as the key and the rating or playtime as the value. Then then projected network from Gephi is imported into the python notebook as a graph 'G'. Using NetworkX, the dictionaries are set as node attributes of the graph 'G'. Finally, the graph is exported as a GEXF file for further analysis on Gephi.

D. Regression

Regression is a statistical model used to model the relationship between independent variables and a dependent variable in order to predict or estimate numeric outcomes of the target variable [35]. The target variable in our regression model is 'Average_Playtime' and three different regression models are utilized to estimate the outcomes of this target variable.

1) *Data Pre-processing*: Firstly, I drop the unnecessary columns such as ID of game, name, developer name, publisher name and steamspy tags from the data. Steamspy tags are removed as the categories variables provide similar information to the tags. Then the release year for each game is extracted as a separate dependent variable from the variable "release_date". A new variable called 'ratings_ratio' is computed by dividing the positive ratings of each game by the sum of positive and negative ratings received by the game. Viewing the correlation matrix of the data, variable 'median_playtime' is dropped from the data as it has high correlation to the target variable and might cause data leakage impacting the output of the regression. Variables like release date, positive and negative ratings are also dropped as a secondary variable computed

from these values has already been included. Further, to use the categorical variables in the data for regression, dummy values are generated for each categorical variable: platforms, genres, categories and owners. Any null values are dropped and the independent variables and the dependent variable is split into 'X' set and 'y' dataset. To make the independent variables all comparable and interpretable, the 'X' set is normalized to center the mean around 0 and standard deviation of 1. Finally, before building the regression models, the scaled 'X' set and 'y' set is split into training and test sets using 'train_test_split' method. The training sets are X_train and y_train while the test sets are y_train and y_test.

2) *Ridge Regression*: Ridge Regression is a type of linear regression model that focuses on addressing multicollinearity and overfitting issues in the data [36]. Ridge Regression is suitable for regression on our data as it is optimal for dealing with highly-correlated data and helps handle overfitting in the data as our data consists of large number of features. Ridge Regression adds a regularization term to linear regression model. The Ridge regression is initialized with a hyperparameter called alpha that mandates the strength of regularization. A suitable alpha value is selected based on a selection of different alpha values and by cross-validating how each value affects the error of the regression. An optimal alpha value of 100 is selected for the Ridge Regression, which is then fitted on the training sets.

3) *Decision Tree Regression*: Decision Tree Regression predicts the target variable by recursively partitioning the input space into regions based on the feature values. It produces a tree-like data structure where each internal node represents a decision based on a particular feature and each leaf indicates a prediction [37]. Decision trees model is selected in this research for its ease in interpretability and its ability to capture non-linear relationships between features and the target. The decision tree regression is performed by initializing the regressor with a random_state of 42 to confirm reproducibility of results. Then the initialized regressor is fitted on the training sets.

4) *Random Forest Regression*: Random Forest regression model is an ensemble learning method that combines decision trees to make more accurate and robust predictions [38]. A random subset of bootstrapped data and features is used to train each decision tree, which is later aggregated to make the final prediction. A reason to select the random forest model is its ability to handle large number of features, different feature types and to reduce overfitting in the data. The random forest regression model is initialized by a hyperparameter called 'n_estimators' which is set to 100. It will define the number of trees in the forest. The model is then fitted on the training sets.

5) *Regression Metrics*: Regression metrics are quantitative measures that evaluate the performance of regression models. Regression metrics help assess how well the model's predictions match the actual true values [39]. Here, the performance of all three regression models are measured on the basis of Mean Squared Error (MSE), Root Mean Squared

Error (RMSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and R-squared (R^2). MSE measures the average squared difference between predicted and true values. RMSE is the square root of the MSE and has the same unit as the target variable. MAE is the average absolute difference between predicted and true values. Finally, the R^2 value measures the variability in the target variable explained by the model [40].

6) *Feature Importance*: Feature importance identifies the contribution of individual variables to obtain the predictive power of a machine learning model [41]. In our research, the important features of Random Forest Regression model is obtained from a method provided by the Random Forest Regressor itself. The scores are based on how often a variable is used in splitting the nodes and its reduction of impurity in the model. The top-10 features are then visualized for the model. The visualization is then used to obtain insights on the important variables for prediction of 'Average_Playtime' variable.

7) *10-Fold Cross validation*: Cross-validation is a technique used to measure the performance of a Machine Learning (ML) model to estimates its generalization capabilities on unseen data [42]. 10-fold corss validation is a variant of this approach where the dataset is divided into 10 folds, where the models are trained and evaluated 10 times. The package 'cross_val_score' is used to obtain the cross-validation scores for each regression model over 10 sets of data. The square root of these 10 different scores is obtained to get the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) for each regression model. Finally, the mean of these 10 different RMSE scores is computed to get the 10-fold cross validation metric for each regression model implemented in the prediction of 'Average_Playtime'.

V. RESULTS

In this section, all the results and outcomes for the experiments performed in section IV are outlined.

A. Centrality Measures

There are a total of 29 nodes and 277 edges in the genre network with an average distance of 19.103 between nodes. The density of the graph is 0.682 signifying a dense network. The experiment on centrality measures of the genre network identify a set of spotlight nodes in the genre network that are most influential and important in the genre network. The spotlight nodes are: Indie, Casual, Free to Play, Strategy and RPG. The centrality measures for these spotlight nodes are provided in Table I. Indie and Casual genre have a degree centrality of 1 meaning they are connected to every other genre in the network and are the most influential genres in the network. These two genres also share a closeness centrality measure of 1 indicating they lie at the closest distance to all other genres and can communicate with other genres quickly. The Free to play genre, strategy and RPG genre all share same centrality measures and come behind Indie and Casual games in terms of influence, connectivity and communication exchange. Thus, these spotlight nodes with their high degree centrality and ability to communicate and control the flow of

information in the network make them the most important genre nodes in the network.

B. Genre Evolution

The evolution of genres through the time phases is illustrated in Figure 7. The figure has 5 different sub-images denoting the 5 time-periods; 1995-2000, 2000-2005, 2005-2010, 2010-2015 and 2015-2020 respectively. Each generation of genre network is clustered to highlight the different communities at that specific time. The hierarchy of genre and sub-genre evolution is displayed in Figure 3.

Fig. 3: Hierarchy of genres based on genre evolution from 1995 to 2020 in the Steam platform. The connections are based on the weight between two genres and clustering of the genres.

C. Community Detection

Fig. 4: Illustration of detected communities in the network.

The detected communities are shown below in Figure 4. The communities in the genre network are partitioned based

on Louvain Algorithm which is a Hierarchical clustering algorithm. A total of 8 communities are found in the genre network. The communities identified in the network are:

- 1) Cluster 1: Game Development, Web Publishing, Software Training, Utilities, Audio Production, Photo Editing, Design & Illustration, Education, Animation & Modeling, Video Production, Accounting
- 2) Cluster 2: Nudity, Violent, Gore, Sexual Content
- 3) Cluster 3: Sports, Racing
- 4) Cluster 4: Action, Indie
- 5) Cluster 5: Strategy, Simulation
- 6) Cluster 6: Massively Multiplayer, Free to Play
- 7) Cluster 7: Early Access, RPG
- 8) Cluster 8: Adventure, Casual

D. Node Attributes

'Net_Ratings' and 'Median_PlayTime' are two node attributes incorporated in the genre network to visualize how the different genres are impacted by these variables. The visualization for 'Net_Ratings' identified that Action games have garnered the highest amount of net ratings in the platform followed by Indie, Adventure, RPG, Free to Play and Strategy games respectively. Action genre can be identified as the most well-liked genre in the platform. For the attribute 'Median_Playtime', the genre Indie was found to have the highest median play time compared to other genres. It was followed by Adventure, Action, RPG and Strategy games. Indie games usually appeal to a niche storyline as they experiment with different game play and stories. They also prioritize storytelling and immersive experiences as they lack resources for high-intensive graphics or extensive content. These are the reason for Indie games to be played so heavily compared to other mainstream gaming genres. The visualization for node attribute is showcased in Figure 6.

E. Regression Metrics

The Regression metrics for the regression models are presented in Table II. Comparing the various performance metrics for the regression models, Ridge regression with the lowest MSE produces the predictions that is closes to the actual values. To view the average magnitude of error in the regression models, RMSE is analysed, where the Ridge Regression model and the Random Forest Model get similar scores with 3198.381 and 3224.070 respectively. To view if the model's predictions were closer to the actual values, MAE is analysed where the Random Forest Regression model stands out with the lowest MAE at 259.107. It is closely followed by Ridge Regression model at 274.830. Finally, R^2 value is analysed to identify the measure of variability explained of the actual values. Ridge Regression explains only 1.9% of the data while Random Forest explains less than 1%. This indicates a poor fitness of these models on the data. Various improvements can be made to improve the predictive power of the models. Despite the low R^2 score, the Ridge Regression model is the optimal regression model among the chosen models, as

it produces values closest to the actual values, and explains the highest variability among the ML models implemented.

F. Feature Importance

The feature importance for the Random Forest Regression model is showcased in Figure 5. The most-important feature to predict the 'Average_Playtime' in the regression model is 'ratings_ratio' with a importance coefficient of 0.200. Other variables such as year, achievements and price also have a significant impact on predicting the average play time for a game. Besides these factors, the genre the game belongs to, gaming categories that the game falls into and the platform it is available in also provide significant information to predict the average play time for a game.

Fig. 5: Important features to predict 'Average_Playtime'

G. 10-Fold Cross-Validation Scores

The mean 10-fold cross-validation Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) scores for the three regression models are:

- 1) Ridge Regression Model: 1405.244
- 2) Decision Tree Regression Model: 2159.506
- 3) Random Forest Regression Model: 1610.117

Analysing the performance of the regression models over 10-folds of data validates the selection of Ridge Regression Model as the optimal model as it generalizes the best among other models with the lowest RMSE. It ensures the chosen model is reliable and can be used for further predictions on unseen data, and also for further improvements on complexity or modelling of data for better predictions.

Fig. 7: Illustration displaying communities of genres in different time frames: (a) 1995-2000 (b) 2000-2005 (c) 2005-2010 (d) 2010-2015 (e) 2015-2020

VI. DISCUSSION

This research provides a new approach to analyse the evolution of genres via the use of network analysis and Steam game genres. The analysis of genres and sub-genres evolution in the platform showcased the emergence of various sub-genres from three parent genres: "Action", "Indie" and "Racing". Majorly, Action and Indie games incorporate newer genres and their characteristics into their games while evolving their gameplay and storyline as well. "Violent", "Casual", "Adventure", "RPG", and "Strategy" genres are sub-genres emerged from Action and Indie games in 2000s which further led to incorporation of "Nudity" and "Gore" genre characteristics in the Adventure games, followed by inception of Sports games through Racing genre. "Free to Play" genre was incorporated by Indie games firstly, but has given birth to a multitude of massively multi-player games that are free to play. Non-gaming genres do not show traces of collaboration with existing genres during their emergence, but have been incorporated by the mainstream genres in recent years. "Sexual content" genre emerged from popularity of violent and gory genres, while various action and indie games are providing early access to players since 2010s to increase collaboration and feedback in the gaming community. Through the analysis of centrality measures, I found that the "Indie" and "Casual" genre are the most influential genres in the network, followed by "Free to Play", "Strategy" and "RPG" as they rank high in all centrality measures and can be counted as most important genres in terms of influence, connectivity and information flow in the platform. Game tags analysis in [24] also identified "Indie" and "Casual" genres as influential genres in the steam platform. Such high influence of these genres throughout the genre network makes these genres the most commonly adopted genres in the steam platform. "Action" genre is the most liked genre in the network followed by "Indie", as it garners the highest amount of net ratings compared to other genres. On the other hand, "Indie" games are most played genre in the platform due to their constant experiments and likelihood of incorporating newer features and aspects of emerging genres which is also followed by "Action" in second place. Community Detection identified the non-gaming genres or Cluster 1 in V-C to have similar properties to each other as they lack the traditional gaming attributes but prioritize creativity with engagement. All the detected communities showcase similar properties and share genres that emerged from one another, but "Adventure" and "Casual" games which are clustered together are very distinct in nature as adventure games are very narrative focused [43] while casual games are simple and straightforward [44]. "Massively Multiplayer" and "Free to Play" genres are also becoming synonymous to each other as they prioritize player interaction, social communities and follow a similar monetization strategy [45].

Through Regression, I identified that ratings are the most important feature to boost the play time of any games. It is closely followed by the release year of the game, as older games tend to have higher consumer engagement. Incorporat-

ing achievements in the game also boosts the average time a user spends playing the game, and is also found to enhance player performance in game, and motivation to play more [46]. Another important variable pushing game play time is price as it has been found that lower priced or free-to-play games are more played in comparison to pricier games [47]. Regarding the societal and economic impact of genres, the gaming industry has seen increase in cross-platform games in recent years, with "Massively multiplayer" and "Free To Play" genres being popular in current times that help foster cultural exchange between people around the world. Introduction of "Early Access" games encourage communication between developers and gaming communities. Incorporation of the non-gaming genres into the mainstream genres has boosted inclusivity of creative arts into gaming, which further advances technological advancements in the sector, and helps to diversify the growth of video game industry to other creative industries as well. The industry as a whole has also seen high value creation and revenue growth as the number of games and genres in each progressing era is increasing. The findings in this research can aid industry practitioners to view how how genres and sub-genres emerge and grow by incorporating characteristics of each other. They can also implement targeted marketing based on the findings of this research or just get an overview of genres in the Steam platform.

There are many flaws in my research, which presents many potential for improvement. Due to the significant class imbalance, where a few number of games enjoy tremendous popularity while the others are less well-known, the data quality clearly shows potential for improvement. Increasing the sample size might make the learned insights more reliable. It would be advantageous to incorporate certain game tags into the network analysis of genres, allowing for an investigation of how genres react to various tag dynamics. Given that the industry is constantly changing, my findings' dynamism may change over time. My alternatives were limited by the dearth of literature on my research topic. Additional attributes can be added to nodes and edges to further improve the network analysis. Even if the regression models had trouble explaining the majority of the data's variability, this could possibly be improved with model complexity increase or other strategies. My goals for the future include improving the regression and network analysis models, getting input on my research, and tenaciously addressing any personal biases that may have affected the results. Collaboration with other researchers has the potential to expand my knowledge base and give me access to new resources.

VII. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the evolution of game genres demonstrates their adaptability and inventiveness across time, producing integrated experiences that engage players with a range of preferences. The variables affecting playtime highlight the fusion of gameplay mechanics and engagement that result in immersive gameplay. Based on playtime and ratings, several genres stand out as having a significant influence, which

reflects how well mechanics and narrative work together. Additionally, video game genres have left cultural, social, and economic legacies that underline their greater significance in modern society. They go beyond mere amusement. The future of gaming and its wider societal influence are being shaped by the genres as they continue to develop and establish a dynamic path.

VIII. DECLARATIONS

Declaration of Originality. I am aware of and understand that this assignment is my own work, except where indicated by referencing, and that I have followed the good academic practices.

Declaration of Ethical Concerns. This work does not raise any ethical issues. No human or animal subjects are involved neither has personal data of human subjects been processed. Also no security or safety critical activities have been carried out

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